

FORMATION OF SOCIAL-LEGAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY CLASS EDUCATION LESSONS

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Abstract. *In the article, the formation of socio-legal competence of students in the primary education classes, the formation of basic and subject-related competencies in the education of education created on the basis of the national program, the requirements for the teacher's skills in creating an opportunity for each student-participant to demonstrate his mental and creative abilities in the course of the lesson and the factors that ensure the quality of education are discussed.*

Keywords: *modern education, integration, interactive education, socio-legal competence, competence approach, life skills, quality of education, teacher skills, innovation.*

In the conditions of the current society, culture and educational development, the innovative activities of the pedagogue include socio-economic renewal, fundamental renewal of the educational system, methodology and technology of the learning process, such conditions consist of the innovative activity of the pedagogue, which is the creation, assimilation and use of information, pedagogical innovations, and the content of education is always humanized in teaching. requires the search for new organizational forms of technology. The character of the pedagogue's attitude towards the acquisition of pedagogical innovation and its implementation will change.

It is known that the effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson has a number of advantages. There is a great need for non-traditional education, especially when organizing education classes based on established requirements.

That is, as a result of the use of various technologies and interactive educational methods in the education classes, the formation of social and legal competences in elementary school students, the effective acquisition of knowledge, practical skills and qualifications that guarantee positive results in the thorough assimilation of knowledge, as well as the development of personal characteristics and moral qualities. .

In addition, innovative pedagogical technologies are the main organizational and methodical means of managing the pedagogical process.

The content, quality, and effectiveness of education lessons are based on the general qualification requirements and the curriculum plan, which is aimed at forming social and legal competences in students. creates an opportunity to use modern educational technologies and methods in a purposeful and effective manner in teaching and learning.

In the elementary school education classes, the teacher's regular work on his competence to use modern educational approaches, strategies, technologies and acceptable methods and his further development helps to increase the quality of the lesson.

The effectiveness of modern educational approaches in teaching education is reflected in the following:

- The growing need to use modern educational approaches to improve the quality and effectiveness of education worldwide

- Increasing attention to the organization of the educational process based on pedagogical technologies, taking into account the needs, interests, abilities and levels of knowledge acquisition of students

- There is a need to further improve pedagogical technologies in order to ensure the quality and efficiency of general secondary education in the current conditions where the national system of personnel training in our country is developing comprehensively.

- Ensuring the fulfillment of the requirements of the principles of DTS, which are reflected in the educational programs and educational-methodical complexes created for general secondary education, based on the preparation of students for life and the competence approach

- The persistence of the task of creating an environment of interpersonal cooperation and dialogue in the direction of further improving the continuous education system, increasing the opportunities for quality education services, and continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market.

In fact, the purpose of modern educational approaches is to ensure the necessary effectiveness of the educational process and to ensure that students achieve the intended learning outcomes. The main task of modern educational approaches in educational classes is to enable the teacher to organize the educational process, which ensures the achievement of sufficient effectiveness of teaching.

If we define modern education, it is a holistic pedagogical process that takes into account human and technical capabilities in the organization of the educational process, is designed in advance, is focused on a clear goal, and a guaranteed result.

The peculiarity of the implementation of interactive methods in education classes is that during the training, each student-participant allows to show his intellectual and creative abilities

Effective interrelated use of the elements that make up the educational system of education classes - educational goals, results, content, method, form, tools, control and evaluation - leads to the technologicalization of the educational process, that is, universal design of the teacher's skills, and the achievement of a guaranteed result. .

At the same time, it is necessary for teachers to independently search for new approaches, strategies, technologies and methods entering education in the teaching of primary education classes, to learn them, to be able to adapt them to their work, to improve the quality of the educational process and to meet the educational needs of learners, modern education with their colleagues. enables the formation of skills such as communication and cooperation using various means of technology.

Primary education classes are conducted on the basis of the following interactive teaching methods:

- teacher - student (work in pairs);
- teacher-student group (team work);
- student-student (work in pairs);
- student - group of students (work in a group or small group)

In our research, we analyzed the content of the primary 1-4th grade education subject, using the qualification requirements that determine the level of mastery of the national curriculum and the criteria for evaluating the tasks performed in practical training, the theoretical-practical, scientific-innovative factors of the formation of social-legal competences in students, the integrative methods of the educational process. we clarified on the basis of organization with;

In primary education lessons, a goal-oriented model for improving the mechanism of forming social and legal competences in students is included in the content of consistency, membership and integrative approaches, by introducing interactive methods and non-traditional educational games that ensure the mastery of areas such as creative activities, family activities, public places, and peers. improved;

through the interactive method and creative-educational games that guarantee the effectiveness of the goals in primary education classes, we have developed evaluation criteria that determine the level of formation of social and legal competences in students (knowledge of social and legal norms, their implementation, possession of life skills, possession of personal virtues);

social and legal competences of students in primary education classes: "presentation" of the acquired knowledge through various forms of education, "choosing a partner", "looking for a friend", "fair of values", "self-criticism", "interactive tour" formed on the basis of the method and creative-educational games, we have developed methodical recommendations that guarantee the positive impact of their active-motivational, creative-inquiry, informative-imaginative components on the creation of an innovative educational environment;

We found out the effectiveness of creating an interactive learning environment that forms the qualities of cooperation, friendship, and legal knowledge in students through the application of integrative, universal, contrastive and variable forms of education in the formation of social and legal competences in students through education classes.

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